

Etiology, diagnosis and treatment of cicatricial tracheal stenosis

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Annotation: The basis for solving the problem of cicatricial tracheal stenosis (CTS) is its prevention, early diagnosis of the pathological process after prolonged mechanical ventilation and tracheostomy in intensive care units. The measures described above make it possible to diagnose narrowing of the trachea at the stage of granulation stenosis and ensure its correction using endoscopic intervention, avoiding traumatic operations. With the development of tracheal surgery, fundamentally new operations that were previously considered impossible were introduced into clinical practice: “two-level”, repeated resection of the trachea, resection of the trachea with simultaneous separation of the tracheoesophageal fistula. Combined, staged

techniques are used, when tracheoplastic operations or endoscopic interventions are performed as a stage before radical surgery - circular resection of the trachea (CRT). However, a single developed algorithm for the prevention and relief of postoperative complications in PCT surgery does not exist today. The further development of tracheal surgery directly depends on the development of a set of preventive measures aimed at preventing the development of complications and identifying unfavorable factors that increase the risk of developing the latter. In this regard, ongoing research in this direction is very promising and promising.

Keywords: cicatricial tracheal stenosis, trachea surgery, circular resection of the trachea.

The development of tracheal scar stenosis (TS) is based on a pathologic process that leads to the replacement of the normal tracheal wall by scar tissue, which narrows the airway lumen. In this case, destruction of tracheal cartilage is often observed, which leads to loss of tracheal wall framework and tracheomalacia [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

In the first half of the last century, the main cause of scarring stenosis of the airways was specific infectious diseases such as diphtheria, tuberculosis, scleroma, actinomycosis. In the middle of the twentieth century, during World War II, the main etiologic factor in the formation of TS was mechanical damage to the trachea during combat trauma. Since the mid-1960s, due to the development and widespread introduction of artificial lung ventilation (ALV) and tracheostomy, iatrogenic tracheal injury became the leading etiologic factor of the disease.

Orotracheal and tracheostomy tubes with cuffs sealing the contour of the breathing apparatus and tracheobronchial tree of the patient were used for ventilator. These cuffs exert pressure on the tracheal wall, which can lead to ischemia and subsequently to the formation of scar tissue [4, 9]. This mechanism is iatrogenic in nature and is currently the most common. Complications during tracheostomy and tracheal intubation are of no small importance for the occurrence of TS [2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 11, 12]. The frequency of tracheal narrowing of such genesis on the background of prolonged ventilation, according to some authors, ranges from 0.2 to 25%. It is not possible to reliably estimate the incidence of this complication in patients who have undergone ventilatory support and tracheostomy due to the great variability in the timing of its manifestation. Stenosis is often diagnosed only a few months after ventilatory support or tracheostomy [3, 13, 14, 15, 9].

Prevention of tracheal wall damage by intubation or tracheostomy tubes is at the heart of the solution to the problem of post-resuscitation TS [3, 9, 14, 16, 17, 18]. Monitoring of intramangual pressure during prolonged ventilations is extremely important. It should be lower than intracapillary pressure - at the level of 20 mm Hg. The use of the system of automated control and regulation of intramandibular pressure allows to reduce the frequency of tracheal intubation injuries by 10 times [3]. The use of intubation tubes without a cuff as well as uncontrolled reduction of cuff pressure less than 18 mmHg contribute to aspiration of oral contents and the development of pneumonia. Regular sanitation of the oral cavity and supramandibular tracheal space is important. All manipulations of medical personnel should be carried out in compliance with asepsis and antisepsis. After

extubation or decannulation of the patient, diagnostic fibrolaryngotracheoscopy is possible, which allows early detection of inflammatory-necrotic changes in the larynx and trachea and prescription of adequate treatment, which will prevent the manifestation of TS [3, 9, 14, 17].

When the etiology is unknown, TS is called idiopathic. It is usually localized in the subclavian region of the larynx and cervical trachea [19, 20, 21].

Classification of scar stenosis of the trachea

Currently, there is no single universally accepted classification of TS. The diversity of classifications is related to the specialization of authors and their preferences for different variants of operations. For example, in the earliest classifications proposed by otorhinolaryngologists, the main attention is paid to the localization of the scar process in relation to the vocal folds and their involvement in the scar process. The extent of scar changes was not given close attention due to the low prevalence of radical resection surgeries [22]. Later, N.A. Pautov (1951), based on the experience of the Great Patriotic War, proposed a classification of TS, in which he first pointed out the existence of tracheomalacia areas [23]. In 1976, otorhinolaryngologists C.M. Myer and R.T. Cotton proposed a classification dividing stenoses according to the degree of narrowing of the airway lumen: 1st degree - up to 50% of the tracheal lumen, 2nd degree - 51-70% of the lumen, 3rd degree - 71-99% of the lumen, 4th degree - tracheal atresia. This classification did not reflect the localization, the extent of scar changes, the presence of tracheostomy, tracheomalacia areas, but it is still the most frequently used in foreign practice [24, 25, 26]. Starting from the mid-60s, thoracic surgeons began to

treat TS, and circular tracheal resection (CRT) with intertracheal anastomosis was introduced into practice. Accordingly, more attention was paid to the extent of scar changes as the main factor limiting the performance of resection. M.I. Perelman (1972) proposed a classification based on the division of stenoses into primary stenoses caused by pathologic process in the tracheal wall and secondary stenoses caused by tracheal compression from outside. Stenoses were divided into extended (more than 2 cm) and limited (up to 2 cm). The author also classified all stenoses by narrowing of the tracheal lumen into 3 degrees (I degree - 1/3 narrowing; II degree - from 1/3 to 2/3; III degree more than 2/3) [4].

This classification was improved and supplemented in 1992 by A.Y. Samokhin, who divided TS according to: etiology - postreanimation, postintubation, posttracheostomy, posttraumatic, postoperative, idiopathic; localization - subclavian section (with and without lesions of the vocal folds) of the larynx, cervical, thoracic sections of the trachea, combined lesions. According to the degree of narrowing TS was subdivided into 1st degree (0.9-0.7 cm), 2nd degree (0.7-0.5 cm), 3rd degree (less than 0.5 cm); according to the prevalence - into limited (up to 2 cm) and extended (more than 2 cm); by anatomical form of the lesion - anterolateral walls, circular narrowing, atresia; tracheal wall condition - with tracheomalacia, without tracheomalacia; presence of tracheostomy - with tracheostomy, without tracheostomy [19].

Currently, the classification of TS proposed by V.D. Parshin has become complete and convenient in clinical practice [3]. It is an improved and supplemented version based on the classification of A.Y. Samokhin [19] and M.I. Perelman [4]. The

main distinguishing idea of the author is the transition from absolute values to relative ones, since the length of the trachea, diameter of its lumen are individual in each patient and depend on anthropometric data, physiologic features of the body.

In this classification, TS is divided:

By etiology: postintubation, posttracheostomy, posttraumatic, idiopathic.

By localization: larynx (with lesions of the subclavian section, vocal folds), cervical trachea, upper thoracic, lower thoracic, suprabifurcation trachea, combined lesions.

According to the degree of narrowing: 1st - the lumen is narrowed by 1/3 of the airway diameter, 2nd - from 1/3 to 2/3, 3rd - more than 2/3.

By prevalence: 1st degree - less than 15% of the length of the trachea in a particular patient, 2nd - 15-30%, 3rd - 30-60%, 4th - more than 60%.

According to the anatomical shape of the lesion: anterolateral walls, circular narrowing, atresia.

According to the condition of tracheal walls: with tracheomalacia, without tracheomalacia.

By the presence of a tracheostomy: with tracheostomy, without tracheostomy [3].

Diagnosis of cicatricial tracheal stenosis

TS is diagnosed based on medical history, characteristic clinical picture, radiation and endoscopic diagnostic methods [27, 28, 29, 30]. Patients may complain of shortness of breath of varying severity, hoarseness, and difficulty coughing up sputum. Stridor with TS is usually mixed. In the case of localization of the pathological process in the cervical trachea, the inspiratory component

predominates, while in case of stenosis of the thoracic trachea or in the presence of tracheomalacia, the expiratory component predominates. Tracheomalacia is a softening of the tracheal wall, which, as a result of flotation at the moment of exhalation, creates an obstruction to breathing and leads to respiratory disorders [3, 8, 31].

The most informative methods of instrumental diagnostics today are radiation and endoscopic research methods [30]. The leading role among radiation diagnostic methods belongs to multislice computed tomography (MSCT) with possible three-dimensional image reconstruction. [29, 30]. The primary diagnosis of TS with MSCT corresponds to endoscopic examination. However, according to Hoppe et al. (2002), images obtained with MSCT tend to overestimate the degree of stenosis, while virtual bronchoscopy and sagittal images tend to underestimate [31].

At present, laryngotracheoscopy remains the “gold standard” for diagnosing cicatricial stenosis of the respiratory tract, in which it is possible not only to identify the narrowing, determine its degree and extent, but also to perform sanitation of the tracheobronchial tree and obtain material for bacteriological research. The results of culture of bronchial secretions and determination of the sensitivity of microorganisms to antibacterial drugs make it possible to achieve high efficiency of the therapy and reduce the risk of infectious complications [15]. In the presence of critical narrowing of the trachea, the diagnostic procedure can be transformed into a therapeutic manipulation—endoscopic expansion of the airway lumen.

Treatment of patients with cicatricial tracheal stenosis

The main treatment method for TS currently remains surgical, in which preference is often given to radical surgery—circular resection of the trachea (CRT) with anastomosis [14, 31]. This treatment option is considered by many researchers to be the operation of choice, and it has the best functional result [3]. At the stage of development of tracheal surgery, a circular resection of the trachea with a length of more than 2 cm was considered extensive [4]. Today, due to the improvement of surgical techniques, the introduction of modern suture material, and the development of a set of preventive measures for tracheal anastomosis failure, such a circular resection of the trachea with anastomosis has become a relatively “safe” intervention [10]. Accumulated clinical experience has proven the possibility of performing extended tracheal resections. However, evaluation of long-term results made it possible to determine that the risk of complications in the postoperative and long-term periods is directly proportional to the length of the resected tracheal segment. These studies have shown that the number of complications increases with resection of a tracheal segment of more than 4 cm. However, at present, fundamentally new resection options, previously considered impossible, such as “two-level” and repeated resections have begun to be performed [14]. “Two-level” resection of the trachea involves the simultaneous removal of two altered segments of the trachea, preserving a section of the intact trachea between them and with two circular anastomoses.

Resection operations are more complex and require technical equipment and a trained team. The incidence of postoperative complications has decreased in recent years, but remains quite variable and, according to various authors, can reach

44.6%. Postoperative mortality varies from 1.8 to 12.1%. Despite all the advantages of circular resection of the trachea, this surgical technique has its technical limitations: CRT is limited or impossible when the vocal larynx is involved in the process, as well as with extensive stenoses. Patients with TS, as a rule, are somatically weakened after long-term treatment in intensive care units and have serious concomitant diseases that impose functional limitations on surgical tactics. The presence of a purulent process in the tracheobronchial tree in a patient also increases the risk of fatal complications. In these cases, it is possible to use staged tracheoplasty operations (ERPO), endoscopic interventions, or a combination of both. The goal of ERPO is to restore airway patency with the formation of a persistent laryngotracheal defect and subsequent stenting of the airway lumen with various stents. The need for stenting after tracheoplastic operations is due to the intersection of the anterior wall of the trachea and larynx along the midline, which leads to the loss of frame structure by these organs [14]. Clinical experience with tracheoplasty with the introduction of a T-shaped tube has shown relatively good immediate and long-term results, low trauma, high efficiency, ease of sanitation and tube care, and relative safety. A great advantage is the ability to model the length of the caudal and cranial sections of the tube, taking into account the constitution and variant of the patient's neck. This method has a number of limitations. Firstly, their use is impossible in the thoracic trachea. Secondly, these interventions are essentially palliative, since the pathologically altered segment of the tracheal wall is preserved, from which a new airway lumen is formed, sufficient for free breathing. This causes worse functional results in

coughing up sputum and breathing compared to patients who underwent MDG. Other disadvantages of these interventions are the length of treatment and the need for multiple surgical interventions.

Endoscopic interventions for TS began to be actively used after the advent of flexible endoscopes and the introduction of high-frequency mechanical ventilation into practice in the second half of the last century. The use of these technologies has made it possible to make wider use of old methods and develop new methods of endoscopic treatment [13].

The arsenal of modern endoscopic methods for treating TS is diverse and includes electric and argon plasma coagulation, cryodestruction of scar tissue, laser dissection of scars, bougienage, balloon dilatation, as well as endoscopic tracheal stenting.

For cicatricial tracheal stenosis, they can be a component of complex treatment and performed as a step before radical surgery. This approach makes it possible to abandon open surgery on an emergency basis, perform preoperative preparation of the patient, eliminating hypoxia of organs and tissues and conducting a comprehensive examination, thereby minimizing the risk of postoperative complications and mortality. Despite the low traumatic nature of endoscopic operations, in the intra- and postoperative period there is a risk of developing serious complications, such as transmural rupture of the trachea and dislocation of the endoprosthesis.

Conclusion

Thus, the basis for solving the problem of cicatricial tracheal stenosis is its

prevention, early diagnosis of the pathological process after prolonged mechanical ventilation and tracheostomy in intensive care units. The measures described above make it possible to diagnose narrowing of the trachea at the stage of granulation stenosis and ensure its correction using endoscopic intervention, avoiding traumatic operations.

Bibliography:

1. Kotiv B.N., Popov I.B., Bisenkov L.N., Shalaev S.A. Complex and unresolved issues of tracheal resection and plastic surgery for cicatricial stenosis. *Bulletin of the Russian Military Medical Academy*. 2012;1(37):24-27.
2. Zenger V.G., Nasedkin A.N., Parshin V.D. Surgery for injuries of the larynx and trachea. *M*. 2007:364.
3. Parshin V.D. Surgery of cicatricial tracheal stenosis. - *M.: Medicine*; 2003:152.
4. Perelman M.I. Trachea surgery. *M.: Medicine*; 1972:207.
5. Petrovsky B.V., Perelman M.I., Koroleva N.S. Tracheobronchial surgery. *M.: Medicine*: 1978:294.
6. Kharchenko V.P., Gvarishvili A.A., Petrova M.V., Albekov R.Z. Prevention of cicatricial tracheal stenosis. *Ross. scientific-practical conf. "Prevention, diagnosis and treatment of cicatricial tracheal stenosis": collection. works M*. 1999:60-62.
7. Yunina A.I. Neck injuries and their complications. *M.: Medicine*; 1972:208.
8. Charokopos N, Foroulis C, Rouska E, Sileli M, Papadopoulos N, Papakonstantinou C. The management of post-intubation tracheal stenoses with self-expandable stents: early and long-term results in 11 cases. *European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery*. 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcts.2010.12.042>
9. Grillo H. Surgery of the trachea and bronchi. London; 2004:69.
10. Amoros JM. Tracheal and cricotracheal resection for laryngotracheal stenosis: experience in 54 consecutive cases. *European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery*. 2006;29(1):35-39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcts.2005.10.023>
11. D'Andrilli A. Long-term results of laryngotracheal resection for benign stenosis from a series of 109 consecutive patients. *European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery*. 2016;50(1):105-109. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejcts/ezv471>

12. Vyzhigina M.A., Parshin V.D., Mizikov V.M., Titov V.A., Zhukova S.G., Ryabova O.S., Bunyatyan A.A. On the issue of tracheal stenosis. *Anesthesiology and resuscitation*. 2005;6:70-75.
13. Lukomsky G.I., Ovchinnikov A.A., Weisberg L.A. Endotracheal electrosurgery. *Surgery of the trachea and bronchi*. 1986:76-78.
14. Parshin V.D., Porkhanov V.A. *Tracheal surgery with an atlas of operative surgery*. M.: Aldi-print; 2010:480.
15. Inozemtsev E.O., Skvortsov M.B., Makhutov V.N., Lepekhova S.N., Grigoriev E.G. Circular resection of the trachea for cicatricial stenosis. *Acta Biomedica Scientifica*. 2016;1(4):150-155. <https://doi.org/10.12737/23004>
16. Tatur A.A. Prevention of the development of cicatricial tracheal stenosis and tracheoesophageal fistulas. *Military medicine*. 2014;1:128-132.
17. Kim S, Khalpey Z, Hsu C, Little A. Changes in Tracheostomy- and Intubation-Related Tracheal Stenosis: Implications for Surgery. *Ann Thorac Surg*. 2017;104(3):964-970. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.athoracsur.2017.03.063>
18. Pearson F, Andrews M. Detection and Management of Tracheal Stenosis Following Cuffed Tube Tracheostomy. *Ann Thorac Surg*. 1971;12(4):359-374. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0003-4975\(10\)65137-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0003-4975(10)65137-5)
19. Novikov V.N., Trishkin D.V., Perevezentsev I.A., Lozhkina N.V. Algorithm for the treatment of postintubation cicatricial stenosis of the larynx and trachea. *Surgical practice*. 2013;1:5-8.
20. Bagheri R. Outcome of surgical treatment for proximal long segment post intubation tracheal stenosis. *Journal of Cardiothoracic Surgery*. 2013; 1;8:35. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1749-8090-8-35>
21. Costantino C. Idiopathic laryngotracheal stenosis. *J Thorac Dis*. 2016;8:204-209.
22. Poddubny B.K., Belousova N.V., Ungiadze G.V. Diagnostic and therapeutic endoscopy of the upper respiratory tract. M.: Practical medicine; 2006:256.
23. Pautov N.A. Treatment of chronic laryngeal stenosis. Experience of Soviet medicine in the Great Patriotic War of 1941-1945. M. 1951;8:220-245.
24. Myer C, O'Connor D, Cotton R. Proposed Grading System for Subglottic Stenosis Based on Endotracheal Tube Sizes. *Annals of Otology, Rhinology & Laryngology*. 1994;103(4):319-323. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000348949410300410>
25. Ozkul Y, Songu M, Ozturkcan S, et al. Tracheal Resection With Primary Anastomosis. *Journal of Craniofacial Surgery*. 2015;26(6):1933-1935. <https://doi.org/10.1097/scs.0000000000001920>

26. Cui PC. Segmental tracheal resection and anastomosis for the treatment of cicatricial stenosis in cervical tracheal. *Zhonghua Er Bi Yan Hou Tou Jing Wai Ke Za Zhi*. 2016;51(2):95-99.
27. Parshin V.D., Koroleva I.M., Mishchenko M.A., Parshin V.V. Diagnosis and treatment of acquired tracheomalacia in patients with cicatricial tracheal stenosis. *Surgery. Journal named after N.I. Pirogov*. 2016;(8):73-82. <https://doi.org/10.17116/hirurgia2016873-82>
28. Parshin V.D., Koroleva I.M., Mishchenko M.A. Evolution of methods for diagnosing cicatricial tracheal stenosis and tracheomalacia. *Surgery. Journal named after N.I. Pirogov*. 2016;(5):17-25. <https://doi.org/10.17116/hirurgia2016517-25>
29. Chernova E.A., Kim S.Yu., Khovrin V.V., Sandrikov V.A., Parshin V.D. Review of the capabilities of radiation methods for studying cicatricial tracheal stenosis. *Russian electronic journal of radiology diagnostics*. 2012;2:2:647-649.
30. Perevoznikova I.A., Kozak A.R. Complex radiodiagnosis of cicatricial tracheal stenosis. *Radiation diagnostics and therapy*. 2010;3(1):33-38.
31. Biryukov Yu.V., Koroleva N.S., Zenger V.G., Samokhin A.Ya. Application of T-shaped silicone tube in tracheal surgery. *Methodological recommendations*